

Table 3. Distribution and prevalence of races of *P. oryzae* in Argentina.

Region	Races
Entre Rios:	
Concepcion del Uruguay	IA ₂ , Unidentified
Villaguay	II ₁
Chaco	IB ₁₀ and ID ₁₁
Formosa	IA ₆ and IB ₉
Santa Fe	IA ₁₂₆
Buenos Aires:	
La Plata	IA ₃₈ and IA ₉
Unknown	IF ₃

new group, II, characterized by a resistant reaction on all eight IRBD varieties. No isolates of IC, IE, IG, or IH were detected. Isolate G4-78 was not identified. The most prevalent race group was IA (40%) followed by IB (16%), II₁ (16%), and ID and IF (8%). The four commercial varieties were susceptible to most races (Table 2). The geographical distribution of races is shown in Table 3. The prevalent races in Argentina are similar to those in Colombia as reported by Galvez in 1971. No correlation between colony type and pathogenicity was obtained. ■

Correlation of rice varietal reaction to brown spot disease and postinfectious production of fungitoxic substance

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There is good evidence that rice plants produce phytoalexin-like fungitoxic substances. A basic postulate of the phytoalexin concept is that host varieties differ in speed of phytoalexin production when infected; resistant varieties produce more than susceptible varieties. Our two experiments on brown spot disease of rice provide some relevant information.

Pot-grown, 3-week-old plants representing 9 varieties were artificially inoculated with a virulent isolate of *Helminthosporium oryzae*; symptoms were assessed 4 days later to compute a disease index on the basis of both the number and size of lesions. Diffusates

Reactions of rice cultivars to infection with *H. oryzae* and fungitoxicity in diffusates from infected plants. West Bengal, India.

Cultivar	Experiment 1			Experiment 2		
	Mean lesion size, length x breadth (mm)	Mean disease index/plant	Inhibition (%) of germ tube growth ^a	Mean no. of spots/plant	Mean disease index/plant	Inhibition (%) of germ tube growth ^a
Benibhog	2.61 x 0.51	10.4	6.2	41.7	11.9	8.3
Dharial	2.13 x 0.58	9.4	21.2	37.5	10.4	25.2
Dular	2.15 x 0.40	1.2	25.4			
Badkalam				40.4	9.6	34.1
IR8				36.8	8.2	35.9
Padma				34.6	5.2	41.5
Lathisail	2.10 x 0.32	4.1	55.4			
AC1351				41.4	4.8	70.0
CH13	1.83 x 0.25	3.5	65.9	34.5	3.6	71.8

^a Values indicate percentage reduction in germ tube growth in the diffusate from inoculated plants in terms of that in the diffusate from uninoculated plants.

from the leaves of both uninoculated and inoculated plants (collected 3 days after inoculation) were assayed for toxic action against spore germination of the pathogen.

The general trend in both experiments was the same (see table). The diffusate from inoculated Benibhog plants, which had the highest mean disease index and lesions of largest mean size, exhibited the least fungitoxicity. CH13 plants had the lowest disease index and the smallest mean size of lesions. The CH13 leaf diffusate showed the highest fungitoxicity. Other varieties between these two extremes showed an inverse correlation between disease index and fungitoxicity

in leaf diffusate, but the differences between different varieties were not always proportional. Varieties differed little in number of lesions, although they differed in mean lesion size. Resistant varieties generally developed more of the smaller spots and fewer of the larger spots than the susceptible ones. It is apparent that the production of fungitoxic substance is more rapid in incompatible than in compatible host-parasite interactions. This may explain the occurrence of more of the smaller-sized spots in the former. Observations are in agreement with the phytoalexin concept. ■

Sources of resistance to major rice diseases in the Punjab, India

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In 1979 kharif we screened 282 of our breeding lines for resistance to bacterial blight, sheath blight, sheath rot, and stem rot. Ten plants of each line were artificially inoculated with pure cultures of the pathogens of those diseases separately. Plants were inoculated at maximum tillering for bacterial blight, at booting for sheath blight and sheath rot, and at heading for stem rot. Inoculation methods were clipping for bacterial blight; Amin's stem tape-inoculation technique for sheath blight;

inserting pearl millet grain culture inside the flag leaf sheath, just above the floret, for sheath rot; and injecting sclerotial suspension into the base of the stem at water level for stem rot. Disease reactions were recorded 15 days after inoculation for bacterial blight, 20 days for sheath blight and sheath rot, and 30 days for stem rot. The Standard Evaluation System scale was used for bacterial blight and sheath blight evaluation. For sheath rot, a 1-9 scale suggested by Satyanarayana and Reddy (IRRN 4 [Apr 1979] 6) was used. For stem rot the following scale was designed:

R = resistant (Sclerotia not formed)
 MR = moderately resistant (Few sclerotia visible inside the stem)
 M = intermediate (Many to abundant sclerotia visible inside the stem)

Reaction of promising breeding lines to major diseases. Punjab Agricultural University, India

MS = moderately susceptible
(Abundant sclerotia visible with partial rotting of stem)

S = susceptible (Abundant sclerotia visible, stem completely rotten)

We found 31 lines to be moderately resistant or resistant to at least one disease. Five were moderately resistant to bacterial blight; 2 were resistant and 12 moderately resistant to sheath blight; 2 were resistant and 10 moderately resistant to sheath rot; and 4 were moderately resistant to stem rot (see table). Of the three lines possessing multiple disease resistance, PAU50-B-25-1 (MR to bacterial blight and sheath blight) and PAU13-8-3-1-1 (MR to sheath blight and sheath rot) have long slender grains with average yields equal to those of Jaya, IR8, and PR106. These two lines have the potential to replace existing semidwarf varieties that have become susceptible to diseases.

A resistant reaction was recorded for 2 lines each against sheath blight and sheath rot, while a moderately resistant reaction was found for 5 lines against bacterial blight, 12 lines against sheath blight, 10 lines against sheath rot, and

Designation	Cross	Reaction ^a			
		Bacterial blight	Sheath blight	Sheath rot	Stem rot
PAU13-8-3-1-1	Basmati 370/IR8	MS	MR	MR	S
PAU13-8-3-6-2-1-2	"	M	M	M	MR
PAU14-3-15-B-8-1-2	IR8/Basmati 370	M	MR	M	MS
PAU29-295-3-B-2-1	Basmati 370/Hamsa	MS	MR	M	MS
PAU41-10-1-3-262-1-5	Phulpattas 72/Mutant 65	MS	R	M	MS
PAU50-B-25-1	Jaya/IR579	MR	MR	M	MS
PAU50-B-51-1-1-20-62-1	"	M	M	MR	MS
PAU122-73-1-4-1	Basmati 370 mutant/Basmati 370	MS	M	R	S
PAU143-B-41-1-1-1	Norin 18/Hybrid 27	MS	MS	MR	S
PAU164-102-1-2-1-1-1	PAU29-108/Palman 579	MS	M	MR	MS
PAU269-1-9-1-3	Sona/Basmati 370	MS	M	M	MR
PAU311-12-2-1	Basmati 370/Basmati 21	MS	M	MR	MS
PAU317-B-2	Jhona 349/Jaya	S	R	M	MS
PAU321-B-19	Palman 579/Basmata 21	MR	M	M	MS
PAU322-B-11	HM95/Basmata 21	MR	M	M	MS
PAU391-B-12	Sabarmati/Ratna	MR	M	M	S
Pusa 37-6-2-3	IR82/BJ 1	MS	MS	R	S
RP633-519-1-3-8-1	IR8/BJ 1//IR22	MR	S	MR	MR
IR5853-229-1	Nam Sagui/IR2071-88//IR2061-214-3-6-20	M	M	MR	S
VI-158	-	MS	M	M	MR
CIAT 4	-	M	MR	M	S
Mehran 69	-	M	MS	MR	MS

^aR = resistant, MR = moderately resistant, M = intermediate, MS = moderately susceptible, S = susceptible.

4 lines against stem rot. The largest number of lines gave at intermediate reaction to bacterial blight, sheath blight, and sheath rot. For stem rot, the largest

number of lines were moderately susceptible. The resistant and moderately resistant breeding lines will be used as donor parents. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Insect resistance

Varietal screening for brown planthopper resistance

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In a greenhouse screening at the AICRIP headquarters, Hyderabad, of 2,360 rice varieties from different sources, 136 were identified as highly resistant and 69 as moderately resistant to the brown planthopper (BPH).

Among those identified as resistant, several were from Northeast India, South India, and Sri Lanka. The highly resistant varieties are listed in the table. ■

Some varieties found highly resistant (score 1) to the brown planthopper in greenhouse tests at All India Coordinated Rice Improvement Project, Hyderabad, India.

Variety	Origin	Variety	Origin
Djawa Sredek	Indonesia	Company Chittari	India
Gapita	"	Enna Patta	"
Mawee	Sri Lanka	Kula Peruvula	"
Umsum	Korea	MHL 1	"
Lua Ngu	Vietnam	Pandi	"
Nang Lay	"	Parakulam	"
Nganetic	Laos	Pokkali	"
Lal Dhapa (ARC7327)	India	PTB21	"
IC25 11 3	"	PTB33	"
IC25 172	"	S 61	"
T2755	"	S 2204	"
JBS1168	"	T3	"
Manoharsali	"	T10	"
PTB28	"	T16	"
A-1	"	T27	"
ADT 8	"	T1415	"
AE 1443	"	T1421	"
Chennellu	"	T1465	"
Chenninayakan	"	T1471	"
Cheriya Chittari	"	Vella Chenipan	"